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INFORMATION PRODCUTS IN LIBRARY SERVICES

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Introduction:

A society that consumes and generates the most knowledge and information is strongest society. Now day's information products play a vital role in libraries. There are two most powerful drives of change in new economy is 'information and communication technology and internalization'. Libraries and information centers have realized that information products and services is very important for improving user satisfaction and promoting the services by current and hypothetic users. In library and information centers, the products usually consisting of materials and services given by library to users. In these products contains books, periodicals, bibliographies, journals and different services like CD- ROMs, Online /offline, CAS and SDI and Email.

In 21st century the success of products or services rely on not only the quality and design but also on the uses byusers.library has to provide information communication through a number of services like E- mail, online database search, CD- search, OPAC, resource sharing through electronic documents, videotext, computer facilities to users .These changes and developments of new electronics information society which will help user to connect with library.

The term of "Information products" describe that 'Electronically deliverable knowledge based products' which contains print and non – print materials. This entire information product we can see in shape of CD- ROM, DVD or floppy disc and also obtains internet and online data

bases. Librarians should be aware that users are having independently searched the internet and Web themselves. With the help of information products users have opportunities to access their data and searches that are geographically distance. They can also view and vision online and print their information.

- **Information product and services**

Now a day the use of internet and power of search engines have change the role of library and services. All the libraries have change their duties and services for users. All Library basic product of library and information science is not only on physical form of books ,journals ,but also on electronic form like e- books, e – journals. There are so many services have been started in library for all types of users in internet. It is the best media to advertise the details of products and services of researcher, business person which is save the time of them and get the all information regarding their studies. And the library has send letter and other information all over the world in inexpensive cost. These services are like Emails, OPAC, online Data Base, Telnet, Web sites, and FTP etc.

- **Types of Information products And Their Services**

Now a days libraries and information centers offers a variety of information products and services keeping in view the demand for information from different categories of users. Usually information products are mainly two types: print and non- print material.

A print material incorporates all types of books, journals, reports, reference resources and newsletters. And non – print materials incorporates tapes, gramophone records, CDs, DVDs and Pen – drives. Some of these varieties of information products are:

Print Materials

(A).Books

All books are available in print copy but now days also available in digital form.E – Books refer to products that appear as single title and in terms of subjects matter. These are usually as fiction or text books. Armens (1999) started that Corner University has pioneered the development of making high avidity facsimiles of deteriorating library books. They can provide books in Internet and also available in printed form.

(B) Periodicals /Journals

Publications released on regular basis are called periodicals like news, articles, publication which is issued by regularly. Scholarly journals are those periodicals with narrow audience and its publication of scholarly. Magazines for libraries provide the serials information you need to build and maintain a quality collection that best meets the needs of library users.

Non – Print Materials

Non – Print Materials are the information given by images, audio- video tapes and wireless sets, pamphlets. Now a day's library plays a vital role to provide information to users so the library needs Non – Print materials.

(A) Online Database:

The stored information on CD –ROM can be accessed on networks are called online data base. These online databases now available on all subjects. In this data base we can store about 65o MB of data and stored a life span of about 100 years.ROM databases are:

AGRIS for agriculture science

BIOSIS for biological science

MEDLARS for biomedicine

ERIC for education

(B) Websites:

World Wide Web is a large impact on mainstream periodical publishers. This websites provides interaction with the library catalogue. OPAC provides the ability the renew or request items of library. Library has developed their library blog to announce new resources or services at the library and interface with staff and readers all over the world. Library develops their own websites, their sets they can inform about various services, products, events and courses offered by library. And that is most important for faculty, students and other libraries.]

(C) E – mail:

As 21st century dawned, another new type of periodical developed as people continued to adapt to new technology. Library distributed information by email, usually to individuals who voluntarily registered to receive them. For this e – mail software is designed, which helps to send and received mails. Document delivery is another application for electronic mail in libraries. Instant and interactive community connected with email.

(D) Telnet:

Telnet is a program of command that allowed connecting to remote computer on the Internet using a user name and a password. These are very useful for pursuing large databases at universities and libraries.

(E) Internet phones, Web camera and Chats:

This services are allows making STD, ISD calls at local rates .while one talk using Internet, a web camera is used to display the face of the other person in our computer screen. Library can arrange and communicated with subject expert and discuss with the users. These services allow the exchange of idea, information and knowledge.

• **Information products and services offered by different types of libraries :**

Library and information centers are such an organization where products are measured on the basis of quality of library services. University Library services are the supreme activity to attract the attention of the user community.

In Academy libraries and information centers provide DDS services, bibliographical services, Literature search , photocopy services, Online services, Reference services CAS, Technical inquiries to their users.

In Special libraries provide Indexing and abstracting services, Translation services, virtual Information central services, Information repackaging, Reprography services, Electronic library services to their users.

In public libraries provides bibliographical services, Exhibitions, Slide shows, Children film shows, Adult Education Programme, Lectures by Philosopher and Philanthropists.

Libraries and Information Centers are offering the knowledge products and the services. These are varying from library to library.

- **Conclusion :**

So Aim all types of libraries have to fulfill the research objectives and ambitions of reader's scholar and staff. But now the concept is change and all libraries are shift from traditional library services to digital library services for satisfy growing and varies needs of users. Information is a vital resource for national development. Online and Offline services made the users to be more responsible in finding the right information to their readers. University library services are the supreme activity to attract the attention of the user community. The commitment of the university library is to promote the higher education under congenial condition. Library acquisition, organization and dissemination have to dependent on modern concepts for achieved user satisfaction that is happen with the information products and services.

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